

A STUDY ON CONSUMER'S SATISFACTION TOWARDS DTH SERVICE WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TOWARDS COIMBATORE CITY

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Abstract:

Marketing is a total system of business activity designed to plan price, promote and distribute wants satisfying goods and services to the benefit of the present and potential customers to achieve organizational objectives in this study we considered five companies such as Sun Direct, Tata Sky, Dish TV, Airtel Digital TV and Big TV. In this study used both primary and secondary data. The data was collected from 220 consumers by questionnaire method and simple random percentage analysis is used in the study for the purpose of analysis, the percentage positions of simple percentage analysis used to analysis the Chi square (χ^2) test and AVOVA to testing hypothesis, It is found that majority of the consumer are aware of DTH services through television advertisements. It is recommended to the service providers to make a periodical review of such an offer and introduce the changes wherever necessary. This study reveals that majority of the respondents prefer to use sun Direct service because of reasonable charges, own asset, and better schemes. Hence, the providers shall pay special attention on these factors to make their business more successful and satisfying the consumers.

Key Words: Consumers, Preference, Satisfaction, Service & Service Providers

1. Introduction:

Marketing involves a wide range of activities marketing, to a great extent, helps in the development of the standard of products and services and increase the standard of various Fields. Marketing is a total system of business activity designed to plan price, promote and distribute wants satisfying goods and services to the benefit of the present and potential customers to achieve organizational objectives.

2. Objectives:

- ✓ To study the performance of different DTH service
- ✓ To know the opinion of consumers about DTH service
- ✓ To examine the source of an awareness.
- ✓ To study the motivational factors that influence consumers to purchase
- ✓ To know the satisfactions level of DTH users.

3. Scope of the Study:

The present study helps to analyze the competition existing in the market regarding DTH services. The scope of the study also covers the key factor which influences the consumer to take decision to buy DTH connection for his television. The study focused five types of DTH services i.e sun direct, Tata sky, dish TV, Airtel digital TV and big TV. The task of the study is to know among these services which service is highly preferred by users in Coimbatore city.

4. Statement of the Problem:

Public relation and personal selling are tools that may not provide direct impact but will bring a positive psychological reaction of consumers towards the product. Particularly the DTH services that are using promotional tools may experience the potential use of these tools as a means of creating impact on the consumers. From this, it may be useful to make a study on promotional tools of DTH services to analyze the customer attitude and their satisfaction towards these services.

5. Methodology of the Study:

Methodology refers to the study of methods from which we can obtain knowledge. It is one of the scientific ways of solving problems.

Area of the Study: The area of the study refers to Coimbatore city.

Sources of Data: The study used both primary data as well as secondary data. The data was collected from 220 consumers by questionnaire method.

Sample and Size: The study uses primary data collected from 220 consumers who using DTH service. In the selection of respondents, convenient sampling method is used.

Statistical Tools Used: Simple percentage analysis is used in the study for the purpose of analysis.

Tools for Analysis: The Following statistical tools were used in this study.

- ✓ Simple percentage Analysis
- ✓ Chi-square Analysis
- ✓ ANOVA

6. Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is conducted only in Coimbatore district.
- ✓ The interpretations cannot be generalized.
- ✓ The sample customers in relation to the total consumers are comparatively less

7. Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

S.No	Source	Factors	No. of Respondents	%	Total
1	GENDER	Male	106	48	100%
		Female	114	52	
2	CLASSIFICATION ON AGE GROUP	up to 25 years	90	41	100%
		25 years- 35 years	80	36	
		35 years- 45 years	34	16	
		above 45 years	16	07	
3	OCCUPATION OF RESPONDENTS	Business men	44	20	100%
		Professional	34	16	
		Agriculture	40	18	
		Employed	102	46	
4	SOURCE OF AWARENESS	Through advertisement	110	50	100%
		Through friends & relatives	70	32	
		Through Dealers	40	18	
5	TYPE OF DTH	Sun Direct	102	46	100%
		Big TV	40	19	
		Dish TV	44	20	
		Tata Sky	20	9	
		Airtel Digital TV	14	6	
6	RESON TO PREFER DTH	price	106	53	100%
		service	20	10	
		More number of channels	22	11	
		Special offers	10	5	
		Own asset	44	22	
		Less subscription	18	9	

7	OPINION ABOUT USAGE OF DTH	Very good	54	24	100%
		Good	104	47	
		Netural	52	24	
		Bad	6	3	
		Very bad	4	2	
		Good	44	44	
8	SATISFACTION LEVEL OF SERVICE PROVIDED BY THE SELLER	Highly satisfied	12	5	100%
		Satisfied	130	60	
		Netural	60	27	
		Dissatisfied	16	7	
		Highly dissatisfied	2	1	
9	AVAILABILITY OF RECHARGE	Easily availability	186	85	100%
		Unavailability	34	15	
10	PROBLEM WHILE USING DTH	Yes	98	45	100%
		No	122	55	

7. Findings:

- ✓ Majority 52% of the respondents are female.
- ✓ Majority 41% of the respondents are their age group up to “25years”.
- ✓ Majority 46% of the respondents comes under employed category.
- ✓ Majority 50% of the respondents came to know the product through advertisement.
- ✓ Majority 46% of them are using sun direct.
- ✓ Majority 53% of the respondents prefer for price.
- ✓ Majority 47% of the respondents have good opinion regarding DTH.
- ✓ Majority 60% of the respondents were satisfied with the service provided by the seller.
- ✓ Majority 85% of the respondents mention that recharge cards are easily available.
- ✓ Among respondents 55% of the respondents had no problem while using DTH

Testing of Hypothesis:

Chi-Square Test:

H₀: there is no significant relationship between age and type of DTH

H₁: there is no significant relationship between monthly income and the type of DTH

Variables	Calculate Value	Degree of Freedom	Table Value	Accepted/ rejected	Level of significance
Age and type of DTH	35.18	12	28.3	Rejected	5%
Monthly income and type of DTH	32.74	12	28.3	Rejected	5%

Interpretation:

The calculated value of chi-square is more than the table value at 5% level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a relationship between age and type of DTH using by respondents.

The calculated value of chi-square is more than the table value at 5% level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a relationship between monthly income and type of DTH using by respondents.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA):

Relationship between Age and Types of DTH:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between age and type of DTH

Variables	Source of Variation	Sum of Square	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	Variance Ratio	5% Factor Limit
Age and type of DTH	Between column	470	4	117.5	0.1034	3.25
	Between row	118	3	39.33	0.02597	3.49
	Residual factor	4544	12	4544		

Between Column:

The calculated value of 0.1034 is less than the table value of 3.25 at 5% level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is no significant relationship between age and type of DTH.

Between Row:

The calculated value of 0.0259 is less than the table value of 3.49 at 5% level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is no significant relationship between age and type of DTH.

Relationship between Monthly Income and Type of DTH:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between monthly income and the type of DTH

Variables	Source of Variation	Sum of Square	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	Variance Ratio	5% Factor Limit
Monthly income and type of DTH	Between column	387.2	4	96.8	0.2001	3.25
	Between row	2010	3	670	1.0388	3.49
	Residual factor	1934.8	12	1934.8		

Between Column:

The calculated value of 0.2001 is less than the table value of 3.25 at 5% level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is no significant relationship between monthly income and type of DTH.

Between Row:

The calculated value of 1.0388 is less than the table value of 3.49 at 5% level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is no significant relationship between age and type of DTH.

8. Recommendations:

- ✓ To provide more channels according to the preference of the consumers
- ✓ To facilitate frequent signal in DTH.
- ✓ To Improve the Quality of Service like Cable Connection
- ✓ Recharge Cards May Be Provided Easy To Consumers
- ✓ Offer different package structure for urban and rural market
- ✓ To attract the city people provide with more HD channel and introduce more foreign channels

9. Conclusion:

Like that of manufacturing organizations, service organizations also face problems of marketing. The use of single promotional tool or combination of tools is

normally determined by various factors such as market conditions, market forces, behavioral pattern of consumer etc. The present study reveals that the majority of the respondents prefer to use Sun direct because of its best picture quality, reasonable price, various kinds of packages and more channels. So the DTH service providers must pay attentions picture quality, reasonable price rather than other factors to make their business more successful and satisfy the consumer.

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